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Research Article

**TREATMENT OF HELICOBACTER PYLORI INFECTION:
CURRENT AND FUTURE INSIGHTS****¹Dr. Fatima Kausar, ²Dr. Muhammad Haseeb, ³Dr. Komal Junaid**^{1,3}Nawaz Sharif Medical college Gujrat, Pakistan²Allama Iqbal Medical College Lahore, Pakistan**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

One of the major worldwide cause of gastric malignancies such as mucosa associated lymphoid tissue lymphoma, peptic ulcer and gastric adenocarcinoma is Helicobacter pylori (H. pylori). The treatment of H. pylori is still a daunting task for the clinicians because for successful therapy, successful eradication of this microbe is imperative. Primary or secondary determinants like mucosal drug concentration, patient compliance, antibiotic resistance, cost and side- effect profile. However, no new drug has been introduced yet, so the current therapy relies upon a mixture of antibiotics used for its treatment and anti – secretory agents. Various treatment regimens like double therapy, quadruplet therapy are also in practice, but Levofloxacin containing triple treatment is best known for finely fighting against H. pylori after first line battle. One issue that is very prominent is the development of drug resistance in the microbe. Therefore, the future of probiotic medication, phytomedicine and H. pylori vaccine look more promising against H. pylori and its diseases. This review paper encompasses these current and future perspectives of the treatment of H. pylori.

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INTRODUCTION:

A gram negative micro aerophilic bacterium, which is spiral in shape with a flagellum is known as *Helicobacter pylori* in the world of microbes. ¹ It colonizes in the gastric mucosa of humans and is known for the last decades for its infectious properties. It influences almost 50 to 75% of the world's population. ² Many upper gastrointestinal diseases like peptic ulcer, chronic gastritis, gastric cancer, and gastric mucosal-associated lymphoid tissue lymphoma are all caused by *H. pylori*. ³ Along with these problems, it can also cause chronic and low grade inflammation in the mucosal lining that could lead to metabolic disorders. Studies have correlated *H. pylori* infection with insulin resistance, decrease of high density lipoprotein and increased total and low density lipoprotein. ⁴

A variety of treatment regimens are proposed by the doctors for its treatment, but till now the most effective one found is triple therapy. But, PPI (Proton Pump Inhibitor) triple therapy is also losing its efficacy for *H. pylori* because the microbe is gradually developing drug resistance and its cure rates is declined to 50- 70 %. The decreased eradication rate has pushed the clinicians to find new and better cure.

Therapeutic Options

- **Antimicrobial Agents**

The prevalence of antibiotic resistance to various antimicrobial drugs varies from region to region and the consumption of antibiotic generation in those regions. The most commonly administered antibiotics are macrolide, imidazole, amoxicillin, tetracycline, furazolidon and rifabutin. Bismuth is a very heavy metal with anti- *H. pylori* properties. It is used in quadruple therapy and has shown eradication rates independent of antibiotic resistance. ⁵

A survey was conducted in Vietnam from July 2013 to July 2015 on the commonly used antibiotic and its resistance, it showed that 43% of the patients were resistant to clarithromycin, 76% to metronidazole, 42% to levofloxacin and 1.1% to amoxicillin. Results on antibiotic resistance, based on the survey and study conducted in various regions around the globe on different time periods revealed that, during the first time period of drug administration in 2000 only 0 to 30% people were infected with quinolone or clarithromycin resistant strains, respectively. But, in the second period from 2010 to onward, 42% and 5.3% showed infection with clarythromycin and quinolone resistant strains, respectively. ⁶

Overwhelming evidences have depicted that in order to find an appropriate antibiotic in drug regimen, it is imperative to have information on antibiotic susceptibility of the *H. pylori* bacterium within various geographical regions of the world to successfully fight against its infections. ⁷

- **Antisecretory agents- PPI**

The treatment of *H. pylori* involves a combination of antimicrobial and antisecretory agents for one to two weeks. H^+/K^+ adenosine triphosphatase of parietal cells are inhibited by PPIs, it is the enzyme which is present in canalicular membrane of gastric parietal cells and is responsible for the end release of gastric acid secretion. This enzyme inhibitors are more effective than H_2 receptor antagonists in the suppression of gastric acid release.

Under the acidic environment, PPIs (acid activated pro drug) converts into a spiro intermediate of dihydrobenzimidazole. It then changes into an aromatized sulfenic acid which after dehydration forms tetracyclic sulfonamide. PPIs, in this way, binds with different cysteines in the alpha subunit of hydrogen or potassium positive ATPase, which ultimately inhibits the enzyme. PPIs with this anti-secretory properties reduces the stomach acid production, which in turn aids in the healing of tissue damage by the *H. pylori* infection. It also helps the acid liable antibiotics stable and more effective by increasing the gastric pH, and it may also aid in transporting antibiotics from plasma to gastric juices by altering luminal concentrations and rising the eradication success rate. ⁸

Future Perspectives

Point mutation in the *H. pylori* DNA and overuse of antibiotics are the main causes of the increased resistance to antibiotics. Currently, it is widely accepted that the use of antibiotics for more than two weeks or high PPI dose can cause undesirable side effects and complaints.

A report, based on the data gathered from different regions of the world states that a treatment regimen in one area can be very beneficial while the same regimen can be unsatisfactory in the other region. For instance, in 2010, an *H. pylori* strain was taken from a woman with gastric cancer. She was 31 years old and was resistant to almost all the seven antibiotics that were tested on her: Tetracycline, furazolidone, amoxicillin, metronidazole, clarithromycin, ciprofloxacin and erythromycin. ^{9, 10}

Therefore, it was felt mandatory to look out for the new and alternative treatment regimen for the eradication of *H. pylori* to stop the spread of harmful infectious diseases.

- **Probiotics**

Probiotics are live microorganisms, usually within the genus of *Bifido*, *Lactobacillus*, and *Saccharomyces*, which when taken or administered in appropriate amount, leaves positive health benefits on the host.¹¹

At present, the interest encompasses the impacts of these probiotics against a fight to *H. pylori*. These probiotics reduce the *H. pylori* colonization and decreases the gastric inflammation. Probiotic bacteria can alter the activity of *H. pylori* by two mechanisms; immunological e.g, reduction of cytokine profiles like IL-6 and increment of serum IgA, and non-immunological e.g, antagonism and competition with the pathogen.

It is found that the use of probiotics alone isn't 100% effective. Addition of PPI based triple therapy with yogurt was more effective, but the side effects were same as those observed in the triple treatment regimen alone. Later on, further research in 2014 showed that if specific strains of probiotics are used then these can be helpful in fighting against the pathogen, in spite of using any kind of strains. Moreover, this meta-analysis found no underlying side effects.

In another study, addition of bovine lactoferrin lead to the improvement of the gastric health, reduction of *H. pylori* at a significant rate and probiotics declined the side effects of antibiotic therapy. It was observed that supplementing probiotics with triple therapy regimen can reduce the negative impacts of drugs and enhance the eradication rate of the pathogen.^{12,13}

• Herbal Compounds

In the recent years, natural organic medicines are hitting the ground. A number of studies suggested that phytomedicine has positive and complementary function in treatment of *H. pylori*. These medicinal plants are safe, non-toxic and inexpensive with no side effects if used within the proper range. It is observed that purified reactions and natural compounds of the plant extracts interfere with the *H. pylori* activity.^{14, 15} The prominent plants found with anti- *H. pylori* activities are Licoricidin, licoisoflavone, eugenol, quercetin, cinnamaldehyde, tannis, sanguinarine, Berberine, polyphenolic catechins, chelerytheine, mastic, protopine, β -hydrastine and protocatechuic acid.

However, the anti-mutagenic properties of some plant extracts are also responsible for conferring resistance to clarithromycin in the pathogen. This evidence provided considerable efficacy of *Teucrium polium* and *Mirtus communis* extracts in preventing antibiotic resistance. Hence, it provided a solid ground that if some medicinal plants are

used with an antibiotic regimen than they can develop more effective eradication regimens.¹⁶

• Photodynamic Therapy

The basic mechanism behind the photodynamic inactivation of the microorganism involves the combination of a dye known as photosensitizer and harmless visible light with a specific wavelength. This combination generates triplet excited state (3O_2) of the dye which reacts with the molecular oxygen and produces variable cytotoxic reactive oxygen species like singlet molecular oxygen and superoxide radical-anion.¹⁷

In a study, this photodynamic therapy was used in which photosensitizer like Chlorin e6 was reduced from chlorophyll, a natural product.¹⁸ This was used to gain optimum inactivation of *H. pylori* with appropriate Ce6 concentration, incubation time, exposure time and light intensity. As these controllable factors were the major reason behind the pathogen inactivation. *H. pylori* is very sensitive to the blue light, so it was considered a novel approach to inhibit pathogen activities in patients who were resistant to antibiotic therapy. Phototherapy with blue light leads to a high rate decline of bacterial numbers in the gastric antrum.

On the basis of a controlled study, it is depicted that intra gastric violet light phototherapy is safe and feasible for the appropriate eradication of *H. pylori*, specifically in patients who have developed resistance to other therapy regimens. White light and methylene blue dye show promising antibacterial effects against *H. pylori*. The primary mechanism involves the oxidative damage to the pathogen's DNA and cell membrane.¹⁹

It is imperative to carry out in vivo photodynamic therapy on an animal model of disease first, to indicate the effectiveness and limitations of this novel treatment. In addition, the cost, side effects, ease of administration should also be taken into account. New photosensitizer materials for better anti-bacterial properties and safe wavelength should also be developed to enhance the efficacy of the treatment.²⁰

CONCLUSION:

The antibiotic use as a first line therapy might be appropriate if the clinician knows the right selection, local and regional antimicrobial resistance patterns and the fine amount for administration. However, development of alternative mechanisms for the eradication of *H. pylori* is found as valuable advancement.

Adjuvant therapy with probiotics, herbal medicines, and photodynamic therapy due to immunomodulation, production of mucin, inhibition of colonization and survival of *H. pylori*, is found to be a better option.

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